

THE ROLE OF MUSEUMS AND GALLERIES IN HISTORICAL SCHOLARSHIP

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Abstract

This paper seeks to appraise history as a product of culture while museums and galleries are means through which both are preserved. The aim however is to critically evaluate this two axial as they tell the history of man and how humanity has survived over the millennia. It is therefore apparent that, these institutions houses things created by nature and by man and in contemporary times houses the cultural wealth and by their functions as well as uniqueness, they have become the cultural conscience of nations; deserve to be studied. The paper therefore interrogates the role of museums and galleries in order to unravel the information and rich symbolic material culture embedded in them as veritable sources of history that can be utilize to create historical and cultural consciousness. Thus, utilizing the quantitative method of data collection and depending on the analytical approach the paper finds that museums and galleries contains huge material cultural content that can catalyze historical scholarship.

Keywords: Museums, Galleries, Preservation, Cultural, Artifacts, History, and Heritage

Introduction

Museums and galleries are storehouses of cultural treasure or memory bank of the society. They provide varying opportunity for people to learn and explore different cultures. These spaces offer a unique view into antiquity that connect with future generations, and hence; they creates a platform for people to experience things they would otherwise only see on a screen. These institutions are buildings in which one finds many things of artistic, historical, cultural and objects of scientific importance. It is fundamentally a source of knowledge. It not only gives us knowledge but also makes us conversant with the culture history, religion, art, architecture, and civilization of different peoples across the globe. As such, many public museums make artifacts available for public viewing through exhibits that may be permanent or temporary (Findlen, 1999), as the occasion arises. This is especially because they offer an avenue for visitors to learn interactively about a particular field of study, which enhances their drive to take an interest in it.

These spaces can be invaluable for people because simple narrative about a particular event or period in history pales in comparison to the actually exhibiting artifacts and art work from the era; most people would rather appreciate physically seeing an object than read about it. This is more imperative because, it is a unique advantage to see things with a sense of creativity and inspiration. These storehouses can foster a sense of wonder and boost self-esteem when combined with interactive learning exhibits that teaches children about application and sharing knowledge, as well as doing things independently.

This is according to Sara Choi “museums offer a dynamic opportunity to expose children to experiences and explore new things in a rich and educational environment. Through interactive exhibits and hand-on play, children have the ability to take ownership of their learning and develop and explore their own curiosities. This unique exposure provides the foundation for creativity, critical thinking, and connection to the world around them” (Wilson, 2017). Not only that, they also offer a glimpse at some of the most marginalized voices in history. Through this people can

learn the importance of other cultures, see and appreciate what might have been life during the period as represented by the artifacts or objects in view.

Museum artifacts can help figures from history come to life as purveyors of tools, furniture, clothing, and material remains of home life for people who lived many millennia ago. Seeing and feeling those things physically allows participants to connect with the figure in a way that is difficult to do within the pages of a book. Something special about most museum spaces is that they are strategic as they change out exhibits, and some even have travelling exhibits that enable people in the surrounding neighborhood access they would ordinarily not have enjoyed. Besides, museums holds relics, evidences and artifacts from ages that may be harness for utility of the knowledge of how human of particular civilization from that time lived.

Museums therefore becomes the bridge that links people to the objects on display, which houses important information how civilization changes from one period of time to another, as these vital pieces of information must be told and display, they has the great role that serves as the custodian of authentic artifacts and its significant value that gives immense knowledge, facts and entertainment as well (Ahmed, Alaa & Muhammed, 2017:1). This apparently give people the chance to look into the past as well as the future, to see where they have been and where they might be, through the lens of museums and galleries. Without them, many important pieces of history would be perished or shielded from public view by private collectors. It is imperative to foster a sense of community, learning and promotion of appropriate institutions like museums and galleries to be engaged in historical studies.

In Africa, for instance, cultural material are valued for the functionality of society before Western incursion on the continent. Likewise the society patronized the artist and other related skills for household appliances and furniture. However, Eurocentric views of missionaries and colonial instruments came and condemned African art and cultural heritage with cognomen like “primitive”, “tribal”, “pagan” (Datok, Ngozi, Odjegba, & Naibi, 2011:245) and so forth. The implication is that these materials cultural lost their authentic prestige and what they stood for in the African sense. This is well illustrated when Akanbiemu (1955) contests this milestone as the “systematic population and forbidding on the painful hell fire, the worship of other gods”. The consequence of this was that “Christian converts either destroyed these valued material culture or left them to rot away”. Likewise also left to rot was the dignity of the African life style of abundant splendor. Stripped of its value, art works became the focus of unwarranted destruction, plundering and stealing by Europeans and their local collaborators.

In addition to this, the imperialists also brought with them the concept of aesthetics and “art for art sake” which is still very much alien to African culture and which in contemporary era art enjoys mostly the patronage of Europeans and other foreign nationals who are now seen to be promoters of African art with a guilty conscience. As a result their historical beginning in many “developing” nations, museums or galleries are seen as storehouses where unwanted material artifacts are housed; in addition, they are regarded as places where objects associated with idolatry and fetish religious objects are kept and exhibited. This negative interpretation of what museums mean has continued to impede their development in most countries, especially the global least developed nations (Arinze, 1999:1)

In spite of this appalling scenario, museums and galleries remains the institutions that houses the story of man and his activities over the millennia. This is because they houses things created by

both man and nature, they houses the cultural soul and holds the cultural wealth of nations and has become what is refer to as the cultural conscience of nations. As agents of change and continuity, they mirror events, foster and promote the best of the cultural ideals of the nations; they can as well create a confluence where the events of today can be exhibited and discussed for the collective good of society. Through their activities, museums can sensitize target groups like teachers, youths and others through popular forum articulates the goals and dynamics for the promotion and better understanding of the heritage and its agenda for cultural relativity and emancipation. The focus of this paper is to explore the role of museums and galleries in historical scholarship.

Museum and Gallery: A Conceptual Analysis

Museums are institutions (publicly or privately owned) which collect, preserve and display objects (both natural and cultural) with the sole intention of entertaining, educating and providing materials for research on aspects of humankind's cultural heritage and progress (Momin & Okpoko, 1990). In this context of enlightenment, museums are obverse of institutions of learning, libraries and other related agencies of knowledge and memory bank. As memory bank preserve the tangible evidence of man's history, creativity and the physical aspects of the activities of man and his lived experiences. These information about the past of the materials displayed; such material then attract, entertain and arouse curiosity as well as opportunity to rediscover their identity in the past and role they play in the contemporary world. No wonder most societies across the globe traced their past through the works of art historians.

Perhaps for this reason the Cambridge Dictionary Online sees museums as "places of study, buildings where objects of historical, scientific or artistic interest are kept, preserved and exhibited". The International Council of Museums (ICOM) explicitly defines a Museum as a "non-profitable institution in the service of society which acquires conserves, communicates and exhibits for the purpose of study, education and fomentation, material witnesses of the evolution of nature and man".

Similarly, the United Nation's Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) contends "museum of whatever kind should have the same task to study, preserve and exhibit objects of cultural value for the good of the community as a whole." Put differently, the material content of a Museum of any society must reflect its culture history. Aluko (2003) drives this thus: "A museum charts the part of progress (or lack of progress) of any society. It is a mirror through which man can look at himself (with approval or disapproval) and he is able to feel uplifted or depressed by his past deeds (or misdeeds)." While the Museums Association opined that, a museum is "an institution which collects documents, preserves, exhibits and interprets material evidence and associated information for the public benefit". This line of conceptualization is now obsolete. This is so as its concept is widen to include the public to explore collection for inspiration, learning and enjoyment purposes (Atik cited in Gunay, 2012:1251).

They are institutions that collect, safeguard and make accessible artifacts and specimens, which they hold in trust for posterity. This conceptualization includes art galleries with collections of works of art, as well as museums with historical collections of objects. As Mike Wallace contends, museums lies in their role as a nation's memory bank. What is crucial about museums is that they are the only source of "living history" and perhaps throw more light on the future that lies ahead (Wallace, 1996). This is that History should be displayed for study not only because it is essential to society, but also because it wears a classic beauty. As a result museums are viewed as the ideal

learning environment, whether it is formal or informal learning, active hands-on participation or passive observation.

Sozen and Tanyeli conceptualizes museums as “organizations open to public established to exhibit artistic, cultural, historical or scientific artifacts permanently or establishment that carries the properties listed above” (Sozen & Tanyeli, 1987:168). The major reliance of the educational role of museums as International Council of Museums does and portrays museums as “permanent organizations working for the benefit of the public by carrying collections of art, science, history, health and technology to preserve, study, assess and exhibit the cultural values as a whole in order to develop aesthetical enjoyment and education in public” (Riviere, 1962:22-23).

It is however important to note that, museums are suitably empowered to correct the distortions of regional history as well as major defects of many educational programs manifest largely as a failure to make good of the content rooted in many regions across the globe, especially those of African cultural values (Akpomuvie, 2010:533). Through globalization, people from all over the globe have become conscious of the cultural relativity of regions. This process of the consciousness of different cultures can be understood through museums. Arguably therefore, a proper understanding of culture can be attributed through the visual perspective, and that is what museum offers their audiences.

A gallery is define as a place where art works are exhibited and sometimes sold (Encarta Dictionaries, 2009). Stated differently, an art gallery can be seen as a more permanent exhibition center or shopping mall of some sort for art works. A museum is oftentimes seen as a gallery and vice-versa. This is because they complement each other. There are many museum of Antiquities around the globe in which are housed ancient pieces of furniture or objects of arts such as sculptures, paintings, ceramics textiles, and other crafts. Collection of the Gallery is constitutive of an impressive exhibits of paintings, prints, sculpture, among others. The organization of the exhibition as identified by Chukwueggu (1998) “is professional modeled” as “the works on display are divided into...at different locations within the exhibition arena”.

As Artun (2006:41) aptly adduce “the ordering of spaces, the classification of objects, their exhibitions help comprehend the relationships among these objects and samples in a three dimensional world”.

A gallery is therefore precisely an institution, building, or room for the exhibition and conservation of works of art. This is perhaps why art galleries are very essential and have a special place in today’s society. Nonetheless, art gallery can offer an open, eye appealing space where visitors can view and appreciate art works. The point to emphasize is that they play complementary role in the society. But as custodians of the cultural soul and wealth of nations, they must showcase through their exhibitions and programs for good. Thus museums can showcase the best of cultures through properly packaged cultural festivals that can attract global audience.

The history of modern galleries date back to 1700s AD, but public exhibition of art can be traced to Ancient Greeks especially Athens during the classical era. Historically, mythological works of famous painters called pinacotheca as well as gallery of pictures were housed in the marbles hall that formed the north wing of what came to be known as propylaca. Along this effort private and public galleries were later established during the Renaissance when there was the democratization of wealth after the era of church monopoly of wealth and property. Following the emphasis on the principle of individuality, patrons and collectors began the match to the great private collections

that subsequently became public art galleries (Datok et al, 2011:250). They went further saying that the collections of the Medici conglomerate in Florence evolved into the Uffizi gallery and Pitti Palace Museum; the Pope's collection became Vatican Museum. Meanwhile Louvers emerged from the combined collection of the French kings and other Royalties. National Gallery developed with the coming to stream of representative Government in which the idea of national superimposed over monarchical order that spread wildly all around the globe.

In Africa, Nigeria for instance sluggishly kick started a National Gallery in a portion of the National Theatre Complex to be set aside as a modern gallery where contemporary Nigerian works of art could be exhibited on a permanent basis. However, the cultural department was created to primarily tackle the exhibitions of the Nigerian art. The failure of the supervisory then Federal Ministry of Social Development, Youth, Sports and Culture and the cultural department led the Federal Government to establish the National Gallery of Art (NGA) in Lagos.

Development of Museums: A Historiographical Survey

Origins of museum concept date back to Ancient Greek myths. Museums in Ancient Greece were defined as “adobes of the Muses” (Artun, 2006:11). The origin of the word museum comes from the Greek word “Museion” which means the temple of the goddesses called “Muses”. The muses were the nine daughters of Zeus. These were the goddesses of arts and sciences. The collection of objects with artistic values was initiated by the Greeks. The buildings are called “Theasuri” (Treasures) were built in centers with political and religious significance (Yucel, 1999:19). The first deliberate effort at development that can be ascribed as the foundation for the museum concept is the Great Museum of Alexandria. In the 3rd century BC after conquering Egypt, Alexander the Great ordered for the establishment of a library and research institute that “would be the center of Hellenic culture” in these lands to bring “good luck to the city” (Artun, 2006:13).

It was a private Museum. This museum hitherto provided the platform where artists, philosophers and scientists freely conducted research (Madran, 2009:66). In this regard, “The Great Museum of Alexandria is the first center for the design of dream, to collect all words and symbols from Hindu, Mesopotamia and Ancient Greek civilizations and maybe from the whole world” (Artun, 2006:15). The first public museum space was established in 1663 AD in Oxford University in England (Madran, 2009:70), this gave birth to the idea of modern public museums. The original owner of the Museum was an English Scholar, Elias Ashmole who built it primarily for the collection of objects of curiosity (curio).

However, during the 18th century following series of agitations that spread throughout Europe for the establishment of public museums. The pressure groups which were classified under the collective name of Museum Movement (MM) achieved their goal with the subsequent establishments of various museums throughout Europe. The first dividend came with the establishment of the National Museum of Ireland in 1731 AD. While the French government opened a Museum in Paris to exhibit Royal collections in 1750 AD. This was followed by the British museum in 1759 AD in Bloomsbury, London to exhibit plant specimens, manuscripts and objects of curiosity. America followed the footsteps of Europe about 24 years later the spread reached there, with the establishment of the first museum by the Charleston Library Society, South Caroline (Encyclopedia America, 1995).

The wind of public Museum Movement that start in Europe then America was to reach Africa in the early 20th century. In sub-Saharan Africa the agitations were championed by the same people who were bent on the destruction of African historical, religious and artistic objects from Europe, especially missionaries and colonial officers had condemned and abused African art works with contempt. For instance, in Nigeria, some scholars opined that it was a Nigerian that kick started the quest for the establishment of museums in Nigeria in the 1920s that propelled the colonial Government to contact Kenneth Murray and E.H Duckworth who pioneered the museum movement in Nigeria through several publications on Nigerian antiquities and culture (Edeke, 2002). They organized workshops, seminars and exhibitions of African art in Europe. Their awareness campaigns on the need to preserve African especially Nigeria's material culture yielded result in 1943, which led to the establishment of the Nigerian Antiquity Service, midwifed museums in that country (Datok etal, 2011:247) as elsewhere in the African continent.

There are different types of museums, including natural history museums, science museums, art museums, children museums, and war museums. The International Council of Museum submits that, there are well over 55,000 museums in 202 countries (Conn, 2008:47-49). Through these museum collections the ancient world is on our fingers tip to know how people of those eras lived, the tools they used and what things they made. Therefore, museums are called the "storehouse" of history or memory "bank" of society (Babian, 2012). It therefore important to emphasize that amongst the world's greatest and most visited museums are the Louvre in Paris, the National Museum of China in Beijing, the British Museum and National Gallery in London, the Vatican Museums in Vatican City, Rome, and the Metropolitan Museum of Art in New York City etc.

Aim of Museums

The aim of modern museums is to collect, preserve, interpret, and display objects of historical, cultural, and artistic, or scientific significance for the enlightenment of society. Viewed from the lens of community, the aim is multiple depending on the role plays by museums. This is because a visit to a local history museum or big art museum can be an entertaining and educative venture (Lipschomb, 2010) essentially serve as a measure to increase the sophistication of its dwellers. Likewise to a museum activist, a museum might be the hallmark to educate the public about the museum's mission, such as environmentalism or gender equity. In that light museums are storehouses of knowledge or memory bank. It is the knowledge bequest that James Smithson proudly desire to fund the Smithsonian Institute when he declared thus, "for the increase and diffusion of knowledge".

Museums of natural history developed in the late 19th century exemplified the Victorian desire for consumption and order. The sourcing and gathering various specimens of each classification of varied field of knowledge for research, educate, interpret and for display was the purpose as elsewhere. Similarly, scientific research was shifting from museums to university laboratories (Findlen, 1994:3) that, research is no longer a main purpose of most museums. The point to emphasize is the question about the purposes of interpretation of museum's collection, there has been a consistent mission to protect and preserve artifacts for upcoming generations. As adequate care, expertise, and expense is required in the preservation efforts to revamp decomposition in old artifacts, art works, buildings, and documents. This is essential that museums display objects that are crucial to a culture. As historian Steven Conn elaborates, to see the thing itself, with one's own

eyes and in a public place, surrounded by other people having some version of the same experience can be enchanting (Conn, 2008)

Furthermore, museum purposes vary from institution to institution depending on what the focus of that museum happens to be, but there are various core values or objectives that they all share, usually but not limited to conservation, documentation, interpretation, education, and enjoyment. Of interest objects must be conserved; their condition not allowed to be in a deplorable state. Hence for validation purposes, objects must be curated; cared for, hitherto on daily basis. They must also be documented; every available fact recorded concerning each object for perpetuity, in a manner that will endure the test of time, comprehensive and understood. Interpretation and Education go hand in hand. While to interpret something is to educate, and education is essentially passing information and sharing it with a wider public spectrum. Interestingly, the digital age allows this to be shared in the comfort of homes the world over.

So, museums are absolutely fundamental in preserving our history. Not only do museums keep important objects, but in most cases they are the only places to keep these items where staffs are trained and have wherewithal to keep them safe for future generations. Also, there has been a huge rise in “edutainment” and “interpretive centers” of museums today (Onur, 2012:166). Arguably, this tendency towards more entertaining and interactive learning means these museums are able to creatively involve people in the past and teach valuable lessons about our history. Thus accreditation is only obtained by those museums which can validate the artifacts and their stories, they are also able to preserve a more authentic history than “revisionist history” in text books, for example, Museums often seek to reach a wide audience, such as a national or local museum, while some museums have specific audience like the National War Museum, Umuahia, Nigeria or the LDS Church History Museum for examples. Of importance, museums collect objects of significance that is congruent with their mission statement for conservation and display.

Although most museums do not allow physical contact with the associated objects, there are others that are interactive and encourage a more hands-on approach. Museums also do a lot of artifact recovery. The Tyrell museum for instance, has a fossil library as large as the museum. They are also unique in this area because one of their exhibits is actually the archeologists in their laboratory on fossils. One can however watch, and sometimes ask questions, as well as undertake a private tour of the collections. In fact, museums are places of enjoyment and as a place for “infotainment”: Entertaining and informative as well.

Again, there is an old saying: “Those who fail to learn from history are doomed to repeat it.” A history museum records and exhibits our history. It is important that a knowledge of who we are and how we came to be tells our story as a people. A people cannot know who they are unless they know their history, and museums displays this in a more coherent easily accessible fashion. This is how most natural history collections were preserved and displayed, with which many species would have gone extinct in the process. The impact is that they visualize. Even those that has little interest in reading about historical events empathize with those who endured whatever historical event is being exhibited. This is that museum aim to draw people into another time period and show that of course this really did happen.

Moreover, contemporaneously museums have become the tools for mass culture. The aims of museums do not only encompass conserving and exhibiting cultural treasures and objects that

provide us with information but include the provision of educational tasks. This is because in earlier stages of its evolutionary trend was object centered and self-enclosed approaches toward human centered and outward looking tendencies to cope with the challenges of the changing world, modern art views and new outlook to museology. Museums however have strategically aimed that objects are not only for observation and created a new field called museum pedagogy (Gunay, 2012:1257). He adds further “they have started to get involved with more projects and keep close relationship with the community to contribute to the education, development and culture of the communities with the help of the share they receive from the public organizations.”

Therefore, modern museums develop and present different programs that can cater for the various categories of participants to be able to integrate their views and experiences in shaping objects and topics of interest and the information created by the curator cannot directly imposed upon them. For example, Museums of Modern Art (MoMA) New York and Saatchi consider the development of programs that contribute to the education and enrichment of children among their fundamental aims.

In addition, museums present various documents encoded to culture aiming to train individuals who are more concern to the community and to the world and they facilitate the establishment of foundations for the development of personality, self-confidence and citizenship. On the whole, museums aim an important role in the integration of various groups’ especially multicultural societies. Accordingly, museums are both social platforms as Burcu Gunay subscribe that bring the region’s artistic life and culture together with their exhibitions, concerts, wide based libraries and shopping centers and modern educational organizations that question the new methods to observe, learn through applications and obtaining artistic awareness (Gunay, 2012:1257).

Importance of Museums

Museums play a crucial role in preserving local culture. With a thorough artifact preservation and documentation, a culture can be recorded and remembered for futuristic purposes. This create a platform for one to share and comprehend the cultural relativism. Museums therefore display alternative perspectives on history. This is especially that many academic history works are biased; dwelling mostly on the account of major culture while silencing minority cultures with groundswell of history need be told and, in most cases, loaded with revisionist contents. They however display histories, timeless, and articulates uncommon history even from those voices that have not been heard before, giving a multidimensional approaches to educate the public especially people have simply never been enlightened outside the dominant culture. This divergent view is something that is very essential for historical scholarship. In addition, when viewpoints are only taken from a particular source without the consideration of other perspectives, it become severally handicapped (oral communications with Professor Abi Derefaka 22/8/2020).

They always creates a linkage amongst people of different backgrounds for deliberate cultural diffusion. For example, we note two categories of people as museums activists in search of information on other cultures: People with that heritage, and people interested in learning about that civilization who come from a different background. Museums focused on heritage and culture bring people together, creating a synergy or network of support for different minorities and groups. It is support networks like these that prevent cultures from retrogressive changes and languages from going into extinction. It is however stated that museums and galleries are important institutions in their quest to prevent culture and language loss. These losses occur when the

minority culture sees itself inferior and strive to look like those of the major culture. By using a museum to cultivate mutual respect and interest in these minority cultures, it is a magnificent push to prevent cultural losses (Ahmed et al, 2017:4)

Furthermore, they educate foreigners about the indigenous culture to be respected as globalization is invading the holy of holies as cultural synchronization is becoming the norm. It is therefore important for those of the major culture to be enlightened about the minority cultures as well as their everyday life. The best way to articulate this is through a display of local culture in a museum. For instance, while one can read about a certain civilization or period of time in text books or print media, it is much more meaningful to sight the art and artifacts in person. It is crystal clear from the above that people with firsthand experience benefit more than people who merely read about it in a book (Smith, 2019). After all, the art and photography in art galleries can also inspire people to create new and dynamic works of art. In addition, many art museums offers tours and even art classes to the general public.

These classes work to educate a new generation of art appreciators and artists alike. On the whole then, museums contribute immensely to society in many ways such as hands-on learning with knowledgeable expertise and visual aids to help inculcate new ideas. This is especially the earlier a child is educated on the importance of diversity, the more likely they are to become friendly and tolerant adults in future (oral communication with Professor Kingdom Orji 28/2/2020).

Museums display alternative perspectives of a particular culture in a visual manner. As such, this visual history provides a snapshot of what life was like at a particular period of time through the art work. For example, the art may provide the materials and information about the people living in a particular time period that enrich and create an experience that is memorable (Smith, 2019). They may also help to articulate the social and political climate at the time the art work was made. More importantly though, the art showcases the view of a particular artist during a certain historical epoch. In some pieces, the art may be more realistic; however, in other pieces, the art work may be more symbolic in content and nature.

This is so that recording everyday activities of a culture is one sure way of preserving it. Many cultures are on the verge of extinction however, careful preservation of these cultures is the only hope a heritage group has for recovering its culture. Such daily activities include religion, art, foods, rituals and others that make a culture unique are displayed (Workman, 2016) by different museums across the globe.

Impact of Museums and Galleries on Historical Scholarship

The chief function of museums has primarily encompasses the collecting, preserving, researching and displaying of artifacts or object of material culture. Over the years, emphasis has now shifted to exhibitions, interpretation, learning and audience. This further underscore increasing number of museums, with an incredible range of themes and subjects offered. Displays are still constructed essentially around objects, thus making material culture a key constituent of most museum interpretative narratives. The fact is that History consumed in museums Alex Werner subscribe is closer to what might be called “public history” than the history written by academics (Werner, 2008).

Despite the rapid increase in museum collections over the year’s historians have preferred to research in archives and libraries rather than in the museum object store. Recently, historians have shifted grounds to other areas especially museum objects as new technology has resulted in

digitized collections being made available through the internet. They have also become more concerned in the development of new galleries and temporary exhibitions. The history of museums and of collecting has, in fact, become a specialist field all of its own for educational purposes (Alexander, 1983:54).

The documentary materials held in museums constitute a vast resource base. This is so because; museums can increase our sense of history, help us feel proud of where we have come from, can inspire, and challenge and stimulate us, and make us feel at home. As society battles with issues of discrimination, intolerance and poverty, museums can provide the platform for people to understand, debate, and challenge these concerns. They serve as the bridge for reconciliation and mutual growth; museums have an essential role to play here. They help us understand our past, to shape our future. This however provoked UNESCO's global action in the promotion of the pivotal role of culture for sustainable development, peace and history through the recognition and promotion of cultural diversity and intercultural dialogue as well as the protection of culture history in all its manifestations.

Thereby denouncing the attacks on cultural properties and the deliberate strategies of cultural cleansing in certain parts of the globe, especially in Syria and Iraq (Bokova, 2014). She thus reiterates global organizations to create protected cultural zones in conflict environments to support global efforts to integrate cultural issues into the political response to the crisis and to combat the illicit trafficking in cultural properties.

They can also enhance society's chances by breaking down barriers to access and inclusion. Museums are performing this through active public participation, engaging diverse communities, and sharing collections and knowledge in ways that are transforming peoples' histories (www.museumsassociation.org/campaigns/museums-change-lives/the-impact-of-museums). All in all, museum's collections ranging from fine art to social history do so in conjunction with community groups and other third sector organizations. This is perhaps why the Museums Association (MA) is vigorously campaigning for museums to develop their role as socially purposeful organization and there is growing evidence that they are collaborating with their host communities and delivering positive social impact on history.

Museums however have a commitment not only to collect, conserve and document material evidence of the past but also to make it publicly accessible. In selecting what to collect, they define what is or is not history. In preserving their collections in perpetuity, they act as a permanent memory store. In the way they display and interpret that material evidence, they construct and transmit meanings to a broad base of audiences (Alexander, 1983:72). Museum displays nowadays, provoke debates in the construction of meanings that support an authorized collective memory, frequently linked to a linear narrative of progress, and an ambition to act as places of pluralism and inclusion that "give voice to the disenfranchised, the oppressed and the silenced (Gable & Handler, 2007:60).

Furthermore, participants of museums are not passive recipients. Rather, in the process of engaging with the collections and associated interpretive material on display, participants add new contents to their existing knowledge and understanding, and construct their own meanings. Coupled with the increasing digital access to museum collections and documentation has added further to the democratization of meaning making (Henning, 2006:137). History is thus selected, constructed and transmitted by museums and then, in the process of being experienced by visitors, it is then

transformed into something else—their own understanding of the past, a type of “historical sense” independent of the professional historian’s ideal (Watson, 2010:205).

In the light of this, museums are viewed in many different ways. They are seen as businesses, storehouses of collections, exhibition and display centers, educational establishments, research organizations, communal spaces and places of memorialization. Today, museums are driven in new directions by local and national government policy. As such, curators continue to curate exhibitions and displays, shaping the main historical narratives and object interpretation alongside their colleagues involved in what is now referred to as learning. This has in no small measure affected curators’ organizational terms over the years and frequently have been disconnected from their museum’s top-level strategic planning. This is especially taking to mean that the future direction of historical interpretation in museums is uncertain. As a result, hidden, contentious and diverse histories are becoming mainstream (Werner, 2008), which has majorly impacted historical scholarship.

For instance, the displays created in 2007 to commemorate the bicentenary of the abolition of the British transatlantic slave trade reveal some template of the current broad perspectives of museum practices. Developed through collaboration and partnership, a co-production with a range of organizations, communities and academics, and backed up by funding, the exhibits highlight currency for robust discussions, giving the main historical narrative of slavery and the slave trade contemporary relevance. This essentially drives that museums are encouraging history to be viewed where possible from multiple strands, catalyzing different learning styles and providing a space for dialogue and debate. The point to emphasize is that they are not the only place in the public sphere where history is consumed but they do institute a unique platform for historical enquiry through their galleries, exhibitions and collections.

Any further discussion of museums and history is vividly illustrated by the American Association of Museums when it issued a publication titled “Excellence and Equity: Education and the Public Dimension of Museums” in 1992, which sought to address the role of museums as educational institutions. The concern here is to emphasize the importance of education in the mission of museums and insistence as at the center of their public activities and constantly search for methods of better sharing information and knowledge with their audiences, as well as expanding the decision making process in museums with models that encourage collaboration and excellence. This apparently occurred when museums faced a lot of critique about their role as public institutions and about their relevance in historical scholarship with dramatically changing needs and methods.

The implication for historians working with museums is that, the document increased in importance in subsequent years as the manner in which they presented history to the public was questioned. Conversely, this scrutiny has occurred because historians have been actively trying to make their work more relevant to museum audiences. The ultimate goal has been to push forward the public’s appreciation of history and its importance in their lives (Crew, 1996), affirming experiences for many museum participants.

While this style of presentation has not completely abandoned, museums have changed their methods in recent decades. They now offer a wider variety of presentations and interpretations of history. These more recent presentations have taken advantage of the new scholarship emerging in the field. They have taken into consideration the idea that history can be explained in a variety of

ways outside of linear interpretation, but through a multidisciplinary approach to tackle the many twists and turns and new ways of appraising and understanding historical events. This mode of interpretation is not to bring about an exchange, but it is based on the fact that new findings have emerged to alter the way people see and interpret some historical moments. This is why many of the exhibitions that museums displays recently have taken into consideration these new research efforts and have inputted such information in their presentations that wonderfully shaped historical scholarship without prejudice.

The results of these efforts can be wonderfully addressed through museums rich exhibitions that look at historical contents in new ways are exciting and make difference in researchers. However, the appreciation for these new approaches has not been totally welcomed. This is so looking at historical challenges in new ways is problematic. For them Spencer Crew argued that, a number of recent exhibitions have been troublesome. This is that the exhibitions have not reinforced what participants had learned in schools. They argued that, too many strange and unfamiliar events and faces appear in the presentations. Thereby engaging the exhibitions made them uneasy and uncomfortable. Therefore, they wanted a reaffirmation and commemoration of the heroic aspects of the history of humankind, their believe systems reinforced, not questioned (Crew, 1996). It is the process of performing this researching and debating as well as sharing of new ideas that make history exciting. The revisions that result are the make-up tools of historical scholarship through a collaborative research goal between museums and academics for fruitful engagement. This approach has immensely influenced historical writing during field work, interpretation of finds and discussions as well.

In the main therefore is the controversies and debate that have emerged over the proper engagement of museums in the presentation of history. The argument is that should museums only commemorate the past, or should they interpret it and offer new modes of examining and explicating history? This is quite ambiguous for a single digit answer. This is to say the fact that museums perform different functions to satisfy their audiences and to factor these viewpoints into the program development process, which enables them to reach a broad spectrum of audiences. In doing so, museums clearly define what is required of historians and normality of reinterpretations as well as multiple points of view. It therefore maintained that there are several mediums through which history can be interpreted. Museums perform this to explain to audience the importance of historical research and teaches the challenges of interpretation and the different conclusions that can be drawn from a single information or artifact. This is because; museums can influence ways of understanding man and his antiquities and that of our forebears and they can help historians to better comprehend the commonalities and differences among human races that make a rich history valuable.

This is why museums are deliberately discussing assumptions that are scholarly significant to historical studies but confusing to the public. The success of interpretative historical exhibitions hinges on the ability of museums to explain artifacts to audiences. To accomplish this end, museum stimulate visitors by offering them information and ideas that encourage them to think and learn. Presenting new ideas and interpretations along with more traditional views is a systematic way to help people learn. Whether or not they agree with the ideas presented is, in the main, less important than encouraging them to critically analyze new information. The fact is that museums as places to experience great things as well as affirming ideas. Thus museums have accordingly

demonstrated capacity in their public presentations thoughtfully in order to achieve this goal. Hence, museums have continued to shape historical scholarship of all ages. How they present their ideas is, in most cases, more important than the specific subject matter at hand. While their research and scholarship is knowledge driven and informed comprehension of a subject matter, their view however is not absolute. This is to orchestrate the subjective nature of the sea of interpretations of a body of historical data.

Thus museums can catalyze interpretations of the evidence presented to them that conflict with their findings, but debate is not as formal in the holy book of museums or direct as it is in scholarly circles, they make people see that alternative interpretations are achievable. The burden of proof is that museums tell the story of people through presentation of exhibition to the public represents one way of interpreting information based upon extensive research and scholarship. However, it is a two way traffic that can adhere to multiple perspectives, which reinforce the visitor's world views and at other cases they conflict with it. For museums, the debate that ensue from their presentation is scholarship (oral communications with Fredrick Obama 12/2/2021). According to him, the key is cultivating varying perspectives in museums are acceptable robust scholarly debates or discussions that brings life to objects.

It is however important to stress the success of presenting history housed in museums depends on the ability of museum professional to collaborate with their audiences to introduce new ideas and perspectives. This is one of the great legacy that museums bequeathed to historical scholarship, if not they will contest "who owns history." The implication of this on historical study is that instead of the contestations, rather borders on the issues presented and the different ways of interpreting their meaning and significance. This is the dialogue that museums as public institution catalyze and sharpen the content analysis of artifacts for definitive evaluation of historical periods through the lens of museum professionals. Furthermore, they will enable scholars to address a variety of subjects, even controversial ones, in a less emotionally charged environment. This is the crux of a scholarly research engage by academics. Achieving this goal demands a sharing or exchange of ideas between museums and research scholars, for the simple reason to collaborate, validate differing perspectives and agree in principle that is "our" history and it often has no one absolute interpretation. This is eloquently calibrated as (Carr, 1961:37) shares that history is interpretation. He went further to say History is what historians writes. It also important to note that, exchanging ideas is the ultimate goal and the element that makes scholarship a worthwhile exercise. It however suggests that without the idea of subjectivity built into scholarly interpretative views especially historical scholarship will definitely be a monotonous endeavor that could have jettisoned the Humanities generally and particularly History into trash cans.

Concluding Remarks

This paper has been able to underscore the dynamics of museums and galleries in the intellectual pursuit to understand and comprehend the totality of man and his environment as well as those things he created for aesthetics, is a collective venture. Although historians have devised ways of interrogating evidences for the reconstruction of history to solve humankind challenges that does not mean there had been no influences from other related disciplines especially museums and galleries. The fact is that, no discipline can claim to have a monopoly of facts about man and his activities. This is especially that history and museums advances the cultural dimension of man and

his creation for both history and aesthetics. This is to say most aspects of the creation of man is stored in museum spaces to collect, preserve, interpret, educate and document material evidence of the past but also to make it publicly accessible. In selecting what to collect, they define what is or is not history. In preserving their collections in perpetuity they act as a permanent memory bank or store. In the manner they display and interpret that material evidence, they construct and transmit meanings. There is therefore a dialogue between the construction of meanings that reinterpret the lived experiences, and the tendency to act as spaces of pluralism and inclusion that “give voices to the disenfranchised, the oppressed and the silenced.

These institutions had their foundations rooted in the material cultural of the people which were the source of not only of information about the past, but also of evaluation, explanation and interpretation (Ajayi, 1990:56) unveiling the cultural messages deeply embedded in museums. Museums special role of interpreting and safeguarding public collections for future generations logically extends to a commitment to study the cultures from which collections derive and to treat bearers of those cultures, as well as the visiting public, with respect and sensitivity. Arguably therefore, museums play a role that serves as custodians of facts drawing selectively on the logical processes of induction, deduction, and abduction that essentially utilized the “detective judicial mode of inquiry,” (Lindemann, 1992:169) is the creative aspect of the dialogue the historian generates up and sustains with the museum archives sources. This is one major role museums influences historical scholarship.

It is however argued that in bringing together museums and history, one cannot lose sight of the core underlying factor, the nature of history itself. Whilst academic historians continued to seek to present accounts of the past that are plausible and testable by other historians, history museums are developing a different sort of history, one embedded in the lived experiences of the communities they serve and driven by community memories. This is par excellence of museums, for best practices to the social community. However the challenge remains that, in seeking to be inclusive of all the communities they serve, museums are at great risk of using the past purely to meet the needs of the present. In this changing picture of what “history” means to museums and the social community on the one hand and between curators of history museums and historians is largely a wide one on another hand. There is little collaboration between the two and this continue to be the case unless research efforts are enmeshed in creating a history museum that is individually research. Above all, museums badly need that academic touch while academic historians, and the discipline itself, could benefit greatly from museums.

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